

INFLUENCE OF ASTANGA YOGA WITH AND WITHOUT SUPER BRAIN YOGA PRACTICES ON SELECTED SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS AMONG URBAN SCHOOL BOYS WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES

S. Pattabi* & Dr. S. Selvalakshmi**

* Ph.D Scholar, Department of Yoga, Tamilnadu Physical Education and Sports University, Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, Department of Yoga, Tamilnadu Physical Education and Sports University, Chennai, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: S. Pattabi & Dr. S. Selvalakshmi, "Influence of Astanga Yoga with and Without Super Brain Yoga Practices on Selected Socio-Psychological Parameters among Urban School Boys with Learning Disabilities", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 31-35, 2018.

Abstract:

The study was to find out the effect of Astanga yoga with and without Super brain yoga on selected socio-psychological parameters among urban school boys with learning disabilities. It was hypothesized that there would be any significant differences in socio-psychological parameters such as attitude and social adjustment due to the influences of Astanga yoga with and without Super brain yoga. To achieve the purpose of this study 90 school boys from Chennai urban schools aged between 10 to 13 years were selected randomly and they were divided into three groups namely experimental group I, experimental group II and control groups of 30 subjects each, experimental group I underwent practice of Astanga yoga with Super brain yoga, experimental group II underwent practice of Astanga yoga without Super brain yoga for the period of 16 weeks, five days per week maximum of 75 min. in the morning. The control group was not exposed to any specific training but they participated in regular activities. The pre-test and post-test were conducted before and after the training for all the three groups. The socio-psychological parameters attitude and social adjustment were assessed by using Attitude Test towards Education for Students-S. L. Chopra Questionnaire and Adjustment Inventory for School Students Questionnaire by A. K. P. Sinha, and R. P. Singh for all the three groups. The collected data were statistically analyzed using Analysis of Co-Variance (ANCOVA) to determine the significant difference and tested at 0.05 level of confidence. The results of the study proved that the two experimental groups had significant improvement in attitude and social adjustments due to the influence of Astanga yoga practice with and without Super brain yoga than the control group. Among the experimental groups Astanga yoga with and without Super brain yoga practice had better significant improvement than Astanga yoga without Super brain yoga practices.

Key Words: Learning Disabilities, Astanga Yoga, Super Brain Yoga, Attitude & Social Adjustments

Introduction:

Education is the process of bringing about desirable changes in the behavior of the child in terms of knowledge, skill, attitude, values and appreciation. For effective organization of this process the teacher should be in touch with new trends in education and should try out new ideas of programmes and techniques experimentally making historical enquiry into their validity, utility and worth-while-ness under the school condition. The emphasis has to be on qualitative improvement which obviously has not received adequate attention of the education. Agarwal, J. C. (1965).

Learning:

Learning is acquiring new knowledge, behaviors, skills, values, preferences or understanding, and may involve synthesizing different types of information. The ability to learn is possessed by humans, animals and some machines. Progress over time tends to follow learning curves. Human learning may occur as part of education, personal development, or training. It may be goal-oriented and may be aided by motivation. Birsh, Judith R. (2005).

Learning Disabilities:

Learning disabilities are neurologically-based processing problems. These Processing problems can interfere with learning basic skills such as reading, writing and/or math. They can also interfere with higher level skill such as organization, time planning, abstract reasoning, long or short term memory and attention. It is important to realize that learning disabilities can affect an individual's life beyond academics and can impact relationships with family, friends and in the workplace.

Since difficulties with reading, writing and math are recognizable problems during the school years, the signs and symptoms of learning disabilities are most often diagnosed during that time. A learning disability cannot be cured or fixed; it is a lifelong challenge. However, with appropriate support and intervention, people with learning disabilities can achieve success in school, at work, in relationships, and in the community. Sonia sumar. (1998).

Astanga Yoga:

Yoga represents the way of life which endows perfect health, physical, mental, moral and spiritual. What is ignoble in man is sublimated to what the most noble in him. To achieve this great art and science of life, a comprehensive practical system of self-culture has been formulated. This system, through the development of one's body, mind and psychic potencies, ultimately leads to physical strength and further on to spiritual consciousness.

The Eight Limbs of Astanga Yoga are:

1. Yama : Self Discipline or Self Restraint. There are five yamas,
 - a). Ahimsa – Non-injuries
 - b). Sathya -- Truthfulness
 - c). Astheya – Non-stealing
 - d). Brahmacharya – Celibacy
 - e). Aparigraha – Non-Convetousness.
2. Niyama : Social Discipline or Code of Conduct. There are fiveniyamas,
 - a). Soucha – Internal and external purity
 - b). Sonthosha – Contentment
 - c). Tapas – Austerity
 - d). Svadhayaya – Strengthening the knowledge
 - e). Isvara pranidhana – Self surrender.
3. Asana : Physical posture.
4. Pranayama : Control of Prana or Life force.
5. Pratyahara : Withdravel of the senses.
6. Dharana : Focusing or concentration.
7. Dhyana : Meditation.
8. Samadhi : Super consciousness. Gregor Maehle. (2015).

Super Brain Yoga:

Super Brain Yoga, enhanced Alpha waves in the brain and synchronized left and right brain hemispheres (Sui, Choa Kok 2005). Increase in Alpha waves in the brain indicated that the body has become relaxed and thus countered anxiety caused by Mathematics in the group. In addition Super Brain Yoga also synchronized left and right hemispheres of the brain and made the brain integrated.

Attitude:

An attitude is a rediness, inclination, or tendency to act toward inner or external elements in accordance with the individual's acquaintance with them. An attitude grows out of an individual's understanding and appreciation of a situation and his emotional response to it. Inner stimuli are involved. The extent to which these inner stimuli encourage or inhibit behavior in a particular situation may be considered one's attitude toward the situation. Lester D. Crow, Alice Crow. (2006).

Social Adjustment:

Social adjustment can be defined as a psychological process. It frequently involves coping with new standards and values. In the technical language of psychology, getting along with the members of the society as best as one can is called 'adjustment'. (www.google.co.in).

Objective of the Study:

To find out there would be any significant improvement on selected socio-psychological parameters due to the practice of Astanga yoga with and without Super brain yoga practices.

Hypothesis:

It was hypothesized that would be any significant improvement on selected Socio-psychological parameters such as Attitude and Social adjustment among urban school students with learning disability children due to the practice of Astanga yoga with and without Super brain yoga.

Review of Related Literature:

G. K. Reddy, Sony Kumari 2015 This study was conducted with aim to see the effect of short term yoga intervention on cognitive function and attitude towards violence in school children at the end of the study we observed significant improvement in cognitive function and mean percentage change is high in yoga (42%) compare to control (24%) and, no significant result shown in attitude towards violence but there is a sign of improvement in ATV in terms of mean percentage change by 3 % in Experimental group. This is an first attempt to measure ATV (Attitude towards Violence) in school children's.

Hafner-Holder S et al., 2009 Aims of our study were to describe and compare influences from a physical activity program and a yoga program on well-being, mood, stress coping, body-image and social competence in healthy people. METHODS: 18 persons attending a gym and 21 taking part in a yoga program answered following questionnaires before entering the program and after taking part for 20 units: Body-Image-Questionnaire (25), Symptom-Checklist- 90R (8), Complaint- List (31), Adjective Mood-Scale (32) and a Visual Analogue Scale for assessing stress-level (10). RESULTS: Statistical analyses show significant improvement in social competence in both training groups; the gym-group report reduced sexual discomfort, whereas people taking part in yoga-group show a reduction in somatization and body-related anxiety as well as an improvement in physical and emotional well-being. CONCLUSION: Our findings support the evidence that physical activity in general improves psychological well-being, however, gym and yoga seem to have different psychological impacts. Future research should focus on comparing the psychological effects of different physical activity interventions in prevention programmes as well as exercise prescriptions in patients with mental illness.

Methodology:

Ninety urban school boys with learning disabilities between the age group of 10 to 13 years were selected randomly from Chennai. The boys were grouped in to three namely Experimental group I, Experimental group II, and Control Group, where the experimental Group I boys practiced Astanga yoga with Super brain yoga, Experimental Group II boys practiced Astanga yoga without Super brain yoga for five days per week, 50 to 75 min. practice in the morning for the period of 16 weeks, the control group boys were not exposed to any training. Prior to and after the training programme the data were collected selected socio-psychological parameters attitude and social adjustment by using the Attitude Test towards Education –Students Questionnaire by S. L. Chopra and Adjustment Inventory for School Students, Questionnaire by A. K. P. Sinha and R. P. Singh, for all the three groups. The collected data were statistically analyzed by using analysis of Co-Variance (ANCOVA) to test the hypothesis. To find out paired mean difference among the groups Scheffe’s post hoc test was used at 0.05 level of confidence.

Statistical Analysis:

Prior to and after the training programme the data were collected on the selected Socio-psychological parameters attitude test towards Education-Students Questionnaire by S. L. Chopra and social adjustment by Adjustment Inventory for school students, Questionnaire by A. K. P. Sinha and R. P. Singh for all three groups. The collected data were statistically analysed using Analysis of Co-Variance (ANCOVA). To find out paired mean difference among the groups Scheffe’s Post hoc test was used at 0.05 level of confidence. The following table shows the stastical analysis of the data collected.

Table 1: Analysis of Covariance of the Means of Attitude among Two Experimental and Control Groups (Scoring Points)

Test	Mean			SV	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	Obtained F
	Experimental Group- I (AYWSBY)	Experimental Group - II (AYWOSBY)	Control Group (CG)					
Pre Test	13.93	13.83	14.80	B	15.02	2	7.51	1.08
				W	604.53	87	6.95	
Post Test	17.20	16.80	14.77	B	102.16	2	51.08	8.73*
				W	508.97	87	5.85	
Adjusted	17.43	17.03	14.30	B	170.86	2	85.43	67.28*
				W	109.20	86	1.27	
Mean Gain	3.27	2.97	0.03					

*Significant, Table value for df 2 and 87, 86was 3.10.

Table 2: Scheffe’s Post Hoc Test for Adjusted Means of Attitude

Experimental Group- I (AYWSBY)	Experimental Group - II (ASWOSBY)	Control Group (CG)	MD	CI
17.43	17.03	-	0.40	0.72
17.43	-	14.30	3.14*	
-	17.03	14.30	2.74*	

*Significant

Figure 1: Graphical Representation of Means of Attitude for All Three Groups

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance of the Means of Social Adjustment among Two Experimental and Control Groups (Scoring points)

Test	Mean			SV	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	Obtained F
	Experimental Group- I (AYWSBY)	Experimental Group - II (AYWOSBY)	Control Group (CG)					
Pre Test	33.80	34.07	32.73	B	29.87	2	14.93	1.47
				W	882.53	87	10.14	
Post Test	29.67	30.40	32.60	B	139.82	2	69.91	6.81*
				W	893.07	87	10.27	
Adjusted	29.42	29.90	33.34	B	266.44	2	133.22	87.34*
				W	131.17	86	1.53	
Mean Gain	4.13	3.67	0.13					

*Significant, Table value for df 2 and 87, 86 was 3.10.

Table 4: Scheffe's Post Hoc Test for Adjusted Means of Social Adjustment

Experimental group- I (AYWSBY)	Experimental group - II (ASWOSBY)	Control Group (CG)	MD	CI
29.42	29.90	-	0.49	0.79
29.42	-	33.34	3.92*	
-	29.90	33.34	3.44*	

*Significant

Figure 2: Graphical Representation of Means of Social Adjustment for all Three Groups

Conclusions:

The results presented in the above tables proved that there was significant improvement in the selected socio-psychological variables such as attitude and social adjustment among urban school boys with learning disabilities due to the practice of Astanga yoga with and without Super brain yoga practices for the 16 weeks. Hence the hypothesis accepted at 0.05 level of confidence. Among the two Experimental groups the Group I boys had better significant improvement than the Group II boys, as it is proved in the Table II and Table IV. Thus it is proved that Astanga yoga with Super brain yoga had significant improvement than Astanga yoga without Super brain yoga. Thus the hypothesis accepted at 0.05 level of confidence.

References:

1. Agarwal J. C. (1975). "Educational Research". Agra Book Depot, New Delhi.

2. Birish, Judith R. (2005). "Research and Reading Disability in Multisensory Teaching of basic language skills". Paul H. Books Publishing, Baltimore Meryland.
3. Gregore Maehle (2015). "Astanga Yoga Practice and Philosophy", New Age Books, New Delhi.
4. Kamlesh M. L. (2015), "Psychology in Physical Education and Sports", Khel Sahithya Kendra, New Delhi.
5. Lester D. Crow, Alice Crow (2006), "Child Psychology", Surjeet Publications, Delhi.
6. Sui. Choa Kok (2005), Super Brain Yoga, Manila, The Institute for Inner Studies Publishing Foundation, Inc.